

Grant Agreement No: 101086276

EAJADE

Europe-America-Japan Accelerator Development Exchange Programme
Horizon-Europe Marie Skłodowska-Curie Staff Exchange Action

DELIVERABLE REPORT

DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION PLAN

DELIVERABLE: D14

Document identifier:	EAJADE.Del.D14.WP6
Due date of deliverable:	End of Month 6 (August 2023)
Report release date:	17 July 2023
Work package:	WP6: Management, dissemination, training, knowledge transfer, and communication
Lead beneficiary:	DESY
Document status:	Final
doi	10.5281/zenodo.8268407

Delivery Slip

	Name	Partner	Date
Authored by	T. Schörner	DESY	03 Jul 2023
Reviewed by	P. Bambade S. Stapnes [Scientific coordinator]	CNRS CERN	05 Jul 2023
Approved by	General Assembly		14 Jul 2023

Deliverable:

Dissemination and Exploitation Plan

Executive summary:

This report summarises the plans, in the EAJADE consortium, for dissemination, communication and outreach.

1. INTRODUCTION

EAJADE is a consortium of numerous partners, working on diverse aspects of accelerator R&D aiming at a future Higgs factory. Nevertheless, everybody in EAJADE is deeply rooted in the overall scientific endeavour of particle and accelerator physics and involved in numerous networks, sharing the overall goals of the fields.

In this context, EAJADE is deeply aware and has a clear vision of the need to disseminate, exploit and communicate its results efficiently at level commensurate with its possibilities, taking into account instruments and best practices already established in our field.

We plan for our dissemination and communication activities to reach the following target groups:

- the scientific communities of the research fields EAJADE is involved with, in particular Higgs factory efforts, accelerator R&D and relevant technology R&D – both externally and also internally to the EAJADE consortium and network;
- young researchers from the wider science and technology community;
- European industries involved in the proposed research field;
- general school and student audiences;
- the general non-professional public.

In general, all relevant events organised centrally by institutions of the consortium members, or to which EAJADE members or institutions contribute, will be shared within the consortium to insure the best possible integration into the EAJADE dissemination & communication programme.

In this document we sketch our plans for dissemination (section 2) and for communication and outreach (section 3). Section 4 summarises the individual measures we intend to take.

2. DISSEMINATION

The EAJADE **dissemination strategy** builds on best practices developed and established in the accelerator and high-energy physics communities.

The purpose of all activities is not only to share the project's findings with a broad community of basic and applied scientists for further exploitation and development, but also to trigger possible technology transfers. The targeted audiences are hence both the specialized research communities and their industrial partners, and the topics addressed comprise the narrower focus of the EAJADE project like Higgs factory activities and the operation of existing facilities, but also more generally the development of technologies and methods relevant for these purposes and beyond, and their potential commercialisation. Examples are beam instrumentation developed through EAJADE that can have value for other electron beam facilities like light sources, or RF systems or special devices that can also lead to improvements or new ideas which might interest industry. EAJADE will carefully monitor

such opportunities and encourage a high level of engagement with the relevant partners and communities.

The **dissemination process** in our fields normally involves two stages: reports at international workshops and conferences, partly with ensuing conference report publications, and subsequent peer-reviewed publications in open-access specialised journals.

For the first step, international conferences like IPAC (International Particle Accelerator Conference) and IBIC (International Beam Instrumentation Conference) or workshops of TTC (TESLA Technology Collaboration for superconducting RF accelerator R & D), organised yearly in Europe, Asia and America, are ideal frameworks in this respect, since they always include a large industry participation. At the IPAC series of conferences, special industry sessions are for instance organized, and the poster sessions and industry booths are physically arranged to maximize inter-mixing and interactions of academic and private sector delegates. EAJADE will strive to make a visible appearance at such events, potentially organising dedicated contributions or even specific sessions in the course of the event. In particular, EAJADE secondees will be encouraged to present their results both at the large international conferences of the fields and in dedicated events like EAJADE annual meetings or dedicated workshops, organised centrally by EAJADE or by any of the participating institutions.

Conference reports are for results considered reliable although deserving further checks and investigations. The Joint Accelerator Conferences Website (JACoW¹) is often used, sometimes with a dedicated “light peer-review” of chosen papers to prepare for further peer-reviewed publication, as well as special support for doctoral students (training sessions on specific topics, financial support to participate). This first stage aims at triggering other work from the relevant science and technology community, to confirm or contradict the results, and possibly develop them.

Peer-reviewed publications follow when the work is considered totally solid and fully documented, aiming at providing all the details needed to understand, reproduce and implement the findings, which includes free access to repositories for needed software, as well as, where appropriate, simulation setups and data samples for cross-checks. We aim for publication e.g. in the journals Physical Review Accelerators and Beams, Nuclear Instruments and Methods A, Journal of Instrumentation, Particle Accelerators. For the most important results, very high impact journals such as Physical Review, Physical Review Letters, Physics Letters or even Nature are used.

EAJADE scientists are fully integrated in this already existing dissemination process. We will use it to promote the specific scientific impact of our joint research with Japanese and American colleagues, thus ensuring reliability, excellence and appropriate knowledge sharing, while adopting suitable open science practices. The EAJADE website will be kept up to date

¹ <https://www.jacow.org>

with the list of public presentations and papers produced, including presentations at EAJADE workshops. News about the most relevant ones will be spread also via communication to specialized newsletters in the different national communities and institutes.

Special measures foreseen to promote and develop our **exploitation potential** will be discussed later in the project, in the course of the mid-term review and in the final report. Tools to be employed are the relevant workshops and working groups, communication in the EAJADE work packages which involve industry partners, and industry secondments. Monitoring and promoting the EAJADE exploitation potential will be part of task 6.2 in WP 6.

3. COMMUNICATION AND OUTREACH

Communication and outreach activities are central in EAJADE, not only general science outreach, but also to bring technology closer to the general public, by making it more understandable especially to young people. The rigorous methods of scientific investigation, involving careful formulation of conclusions after critical analysis and suitable cross-checks, must also be explained and promoted. This is important at a time of ever-increasing computer-based activity and virtualization, with also lots of unchecked information on the internet and more than occasional doubts in scientific facts and approaches. Our strategy for communication and outreach also needs to take into account approaches outside Europe, especially in Japan and northern America, where actions involving schools are often carefully tailored to each level or specific profile rather than a one-size-fits-all approach. It will be ensured that EAJADE will acknowledge EU funding and will ensure its visibility for all communication activities related to the project.

The EAJADE communication and outreach programme is included in WP 6 and targets three main groups: (1) general public, (2) high-school students and (3) university students. All EAJADE institutions already have significant communication and outreach activities (e.g. press offices, communication officers, etc.) aimed at these groups, e.g. Open Days, participation in Researchers' Nights, exhibitions, dedicated lectures in high-schools (e.g. the CNRS "Conférences NEPAL" programme – "Noyaux Et Particules au Lycée"), "International Masterclasses – Hand on Particle Physics" (where high-school students conduct simplified data analyses with LHC data), the now traditional DESY Science Café, Science Slams, Girls/Boys' Days, etc. Success stories are also showcased for interested non-scientific audiences in the DESY research magazine "FEMTO", Facebook pages, Helmholtz blogs, etc.

It would not be sensible for EAJADE to launch a totally independent communication and outreach programme. We will rather aim at making our research and participation of our scientists visible within already existing activities, exploiting and capitalizing on what already works best, with the goal of promoting the specific role and importance of accelerators. EAJADE will thus keep a log of the main outreach events in our labs on a dedicated web site,

with links to other players (e.g. IPPOG, interactions.org, ...) and identify which ones our members should target, for presentations e.g. on the future Higgs factory or the sophisticated accelerator and beam control techniques which we develop, and including their applications e.g. in medicine. In addition, equipment and infrastructure in our laboratories are often shown to the public during exhibitions and visits, including small accelerators, test-stands with beam instruments, or the Musée ACO – Anneau de Collision d'Orsay, one of the first electron-positron colliders operated for particle physics.

We have good experience with this approach from another RISE project called JENNIFER² (EU grant agreement 644294), and we know it is efficient to advertise and promote the European Union and its actions among the general public. The EAJADE logo will be shown on the web site of the outreach event where we contribute, and some financial support will be available from the common fund to be set up in the Consortium Agreement to help cover e.g. local travel expenses, an EAJADE booth, posters and leaflets on our activities. WP 6 will also monitor the participation in such events (number and nature of contributions, attendance) for impact assessment.

Finally, we plan special measures for university students, based on positive experiences we have had in the past of inviting large student groups from local universities in cities where our conferences or workshops were held for dedicated lectures and discussion sessions on science and applications, with help of both senior scientists and young Ph.D. students from our groups. At the LCWS workshop in Morioka in 2016³, three of our E-JADE European female Ph.D. students gave lectures to and answered questions from young Japanese university students, in presence of local media. At the TYL France-Japan⁴ 2015 annual workshop in Nara⁵, a full cohort of undergraduate female physics students from Nara Women's university attended outreach lectures from renowned Japanese and French female physicists whom we had invited, followed by a discussion session. We will encourage and support such initiatives at our conferences and workshops, to enable informing and discussing with students on their future career perspectives, and act as role models at a critical time when they decide on their university orientation. This is important because the current number of students enrolled in science is not enough to cover the needs of European research and industry, with many opportunities and more skilled people needed in all our countries.

² <http://www.jennifer2-project.eu>

³ <http://lcws2016.sgk.iwate-u.ac.jp/Program.html>

⁴ <http://fjpppl.in2p3.fr/cgi-bin/twiki.source/bin/view/FJPPPL/WebHome>

⁵ <https://kds.kek.jp/event/25675/timetable/#all.detailed>

4. SUMMARY OF PLANNED ACTIVITIES AND CHANNELS

All **planned dissemination & communication activities** categorized by identified targeting groups are presented in the table below (including instruments & channels).

Target group	Objectives	Instruments & Channels
Young researchers from the wider science and technology community	Knowledge exchange, inspiring young scientists	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dedicated EAJADE web site, • Conferences, workshops, seminars • Publications • Social media accounts of the partner organisations
Scientific community along the line “Japan - EUROPE – US” set out by the Higgs factory	Knowledge exchange, improvement of scientific results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dedicated EAJADE web site • EAJADE annual meetings • EAJADE memos • Conferences, workshops, seminars • Publications • EAJADE special sessions at conferences
European industry’s sector involved in the proposed research fields	Visibility of the project, to represent scientific results, to identify potential for new technologies and innovation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation in relevant industrial fairs • Publications
General school and student audiences	scientific motivation of young people	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Days of Open Doors • Science Nights, Girls/Boys’ Days • Special workshops for students in frame of student laboratories belonging to participating organisations
General non-professional public	To inform the general public about the impact of EU funding on research and training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social media accounts of the partner organisations • Interviews (tv, radio, newspapers, magazines) • DESY Science Café and similar events at all partners

5. CONTINUOUS REPORTING ORGANISATION, MONITORING

5.1. CONTINUOUS REPORTING

The required continuous reporting on communication and dissemination activities will be organised via regular calls to the entire consortium, in particular the General Assembly and

the Consortium Board (for institute-specific input), and the Science Coordination Board (for work package input).

The calls will comprise structured requests for all relevant information, in a format that can easily be transferred to the continuous reporting system. In particular the following information will be collected for communication and dissemination activities in a tabular format:

Communication Activities

- Communication activity name
- Description
- Who? Target audience
- How? Communication channel
- Outcome
- Status (delivered, ongoing, postponed)

Dissemination Activities

- Dissemination activity name
- What? Type of dissemination activity (meetings, conferences, events, ...)
- Who? Target audience Reached (Industry, business partners, innovators, EU institutions, national authorities, regional authorities, local authorities, civil society, citizens, research communities, specific end-user communities, international organisation (UN body, OECD, etc.), investors, other)
- Why? Description of the objective(s) with reference to a specific project output (max 200 characters)
- Status of the dissemination activity (delivered, ongoing, postponed)

5.2. MONITORING

In order to measure the impact of the proposed communication and dissemination activities, EAJADE will collect material for the following indicators:

- number of scientific publications with EAJADE background;
- number of conference and workshop presentations with EAJADE contributions;
- number of dedicated EAJADE events;
- number of persons benefitting from the EAJADE secondments;
- feedback received from seconded Ph.D. students.

6. REFERENCES